

Preparation, polymerization and characterization of some new maleimides

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Abstract : This article described the synthesis of poly *N*-arylmaleimides and copolymaleimides. The maleimides monomer *N*-(2-nitrophenyl)maleimide (2-NPMI), *N*-(3-nitrophenyl)maleimide (3-NPMI) and *N*-(4-nitrophenyl)maleimide (4-NPMI) were prepared from corresponding substituted nitro aniline. The homopolymerization of above three maleimides monomer were initiated by free radical using AIBN in THF solvent at 65 °C. The monomer also copolymerized with MMA free radically in THF using equimolar amount of the comonomers. All the polymer samples have been characterized by the solubility, intrinsic viscosity, FT-IR and ¹H NMR spectral analysis and thermo gravimetric analysis.

Keywords : Maleimides, polymerization, free radicals, vinyl monomer.

In recent years, there has been considerable interest in the free radical polymerization of *N*-substituted maleimides with various vinyl monomers, such as styrene, ethyl phenyl acrylate, *n*-butylacrylate, vinyl chloride, acrylonitrile, MMA and vinyl ethers¹. The maleimide based homo and copolymers have been found to have versatile applications in industries ranging from aerospace to medical and microelectronics field². Aromatic polyimides have been excellent characteristics such as thermo oxidative stabilities and electrical properties, as well as chemical resistance. These polymers have been widely used for a number of applications³. However, most of the aromatic polyimides have one major drawback, their intractability in fully imidized form. Furthermore, there are several difficulties in processing due to insolubility and infusibility⁴. Most aromatic polyimides produced by the thermal solid-state phase imidization show insolubility and infusibility, which make processing difficult. These undesirable properties, which limit wider applications of the polyimides, are due to their chain rigidity as well as to poor defined molecular architecture⁵. Therefore, the preparation of soluble or thermoplastic polyimides has been of major interest in current research work.

We report here studies on free radical initiated homo and co-polymers of *N*-(2-nitrophenyl)maleimide (2-NPMI), *N*-(3-nitrophenyl)maleimide (3-NPMI) and *N*-(4-nitrophenyl)maleimide (4-NPMI). Three maleimides monomer 2-NPMI, 3-NPMI and 4-NPMI were prepared from corresponding amine. All maleimides are homopolymerized and copolymerized with MMA. The studies of physical, spectral and thermal properties have been carried out in order to characterize the polymers.

Results and discussion

The results of radical homopolymerization of 2-NPMI, 3-NPMI and 4-NPMI and copolymerization with MMA in THF at 65 °C in presence of AIBN are summarized in Table 1.

Scheme 1. Homopolymerization.

Solubility : Solubilities of the poly and copolymaleimides are listed in Table 2. All three homopolymaleimides are completely soluble in DMF, THF, DMSO, *p*-dioxane, acetone and dichloromethane and partially soluble in ethyl acetate and chloroform. HP₁ and HP₃ are soluble in CCl₄ and benzene but HP₂ is partially soluble in CCl₄ and benzene. All three copolymaleimides are soluble in DMF, THF, DMSO, *p*-dioxane, acetone and chloroform and partially soluble in CCl₄ and xylene. CP₃ is soluble in ethyl acetate, CH₂Cl₂ and benzene while CP₂ and CP₃ is partially soluble in above three solvents. All polymaleimides were insoluble in water, methanol and ethanol.

Intrinsic viscosity [η] : The values of intrinsic viscosity [η] in DMF solvent at 25 °C are given in Table 1. The value of η depends on the molecular weight as well as the size of polymer coil in the given solution. The value of η decreases as the content of maleimide increases. Intrinsic viscosity of homopolymer is less than copolymer.

R = 2-, 3- or 4-nitroaryl moiety

Scheme 2. Copolymerization.

Table 1. Results of homo and copolymerization of substituted maleimides

Polymer code	Feed mol fraction of monomer	Polymerization time (h)	Yield (%)	%N	$[\eta]$ dl/g	Appearance
HP ₁	1.0	24	25.45	8.69	0.049	Light yellow
HP ₂	1.0	24	36.96	8.99	0.065	Yellow
HP ₃	1.0	24	39.20	9.15	0.078	Dark yellow
CP ₁	0.5	24	51.52	6.90	0.092	Yellow
CP ₂	0.5	24	55.02	6.96	0.118	Dark yellow
CP ₃	0.5	24	59.23	7.01	0.232	Dark yellow

HP₁ = poly-*N*-(2-nitrophenyl)maleimide, HP₂ = poly-*N*-(3-nitrophenyl)maleimide, HP₃ = poly-*N*-(4-nitrophenyl)maleimide, CP₁ = copoly-*N*-(2-nitrophenyl)maleimide-co-MMA, CP₂ = copoly-*N*-(3-nitrophenyl)maleimide-co-MMA, CP₃ = copoly-*N*-(4-nitrophenyl)maleimide-co-MMA.

The IR spectrum a shoulder peak at about 1776 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the symmetric stretching of the carbonyl group in the imide ring only. Its absorption peak indicates that the imide ring remained intact during the polymerization. The imide group of polymaleimide is also confirmed from the bands observed at 1456 cm⁻¹ (Ar-N stretch), 1335 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretch) and 1190 cm⁻¹. A comparison between monomer and their homopolymer reveals that the 3110 cm⁻¹ (olefinic C-H), 1665 cm⁻¹ (C=C) and sharp band at 950 cm⁻¹ are absent in spectra of homopolymer.

The FT-IR spectrum of the copolymaleimides showed the strong peak of 1635 cm⁻¹ and 1504 cm⁻¹ is due to the aromatic absorption of NPMI compound. The strong absorption 1335 cm⁻¹ is due to the symmetric C-N-C stretching of the imide ring. The molar characteristic absorption bands are observed 1780-1770 cm⁻¹, 1730-1710 cm⁻¹ (C=O symmetric and asymmetric in a five member imide ring and C=O stretch of ester). These characterized bands confirmed that unit of both the monomer NPMI and MMA are present in the copolymer.

Table 2. Solubility behaviour of homopolymer and copolymer in polar and non-polar solvents at 30 °C

Solvent	HP ₁	HP ₂	HP ₃	CP ₁	CP ₂	CP ₃
DMF	S	S	S	S	S	S
THF	S	S	S	S	S	S
<i>p</i> -Dioxane	S	S	S	S	S	S
DMSO	S	S	S	S	S	S
Acetone	S	S	S	S	S	S
Ethylacetone	PS	PS	PS	PS	PS	S
CHCl ₃	PS	PS	PS	S	S	S
CCl ₄	S	PS	S	S	S	S
CH ₂ Cl ₂	S	S	S	PS	PS	S
Benzene	S	PS	S	PS	PS	S
Xylene	PS	IS	PS	PS	PS	PS
Ethanol	IS	IS	IS	IS	IS	IS
Methanol	IS	IS	IS	IS	IS	IS
Water	IS	IS	IS	IS	IS	IS

S = Soluble, IS = Insoluble, PS = Partially Soluble.

¹H NMR spectra of the monomers and the polymers showed the following chemical shifts :

Monomers :

M₁ (2-NPMI) : δ 6.91-6.87 (2H, CH=CH in imide), 8.01-7.85 (4H, aromatic)

M₂ (3-NPMI) : δ 6.89-6.86 (2H, CH=CH in imide), 7.89-7.76 (4H, aromatic)

M₃ (4-NPMI) : δ 6.87-6.83 (2H, CH=CH in imide), 7.87-7.75 (4H, aromatic)

Polymers :

HP₁ : δ 3.5-3.1 (2H, -(CH-CH)-), 7.78-7.48 (4H, aromatic)

HP₂ : δ 3.3-2.89 (2H, -(CH-CH)-), 7.65-7.39 (4H, aromatic)

HP₃ : δ 3.4-3.09 (2H, -(CH-CH)-), 7.86-7.49 (4H, aromatic)

CP₁ : δ 3.49-3.18 (2H, -(CH-CH)-) and (-OCH₃), 7.86-7.32 (4H, aromatic), 0.9-1.9 (3H of -CH₃) and 1.6-2.2 (2H of methylene group)

CP₂ : δ 3.6–3.2 (2H -(CH-CH)-) and (3H of -OCH₃), 7.7–7.4 (4H, aromatic), 0.7–1.8 (3H of CH₃) and 1.6–1.9 (2H of methylene group)

CP₃ : δ 3.6–3.4 (2H, -(CH-CH)-) and (3H of -OCH₃), 7.76–7.35 (4H, aromatic), 2.0–2.4 (3H, -CH₃), 1.7–1.9 (2H of methylene group)

From the ¹H NMR spectra, it was observed that the chemical shift at δ 6.91–7.0 (due to CH=CH) in maleimide disappeared in the spectra of polymers and appearance of peak at 3.5–3.0 in the polymers due to formation of the semi flexible poly(substituted methine) -[CH-CH]_n- group⁶. It's peak in the polymer confirmed that -[CH-CH]_n- polymerization has taken through the olefinic double bond of the imide ring. In the copolymers, the peaks at δ 3.4 (protons of -OCH₃) and δ 2.0–2.4 (protons of methyl group) confirm the incorporation of MMA into the polymers.

Thermal properties : It is well known that polymaleimide is a potential heat- and chemical-resistant material, so maleimide is widely used a comonomer for modification of polymeric systems. Only single step degradation at temperature of over 300 °C was observed for poly (MI) in TGA. The thermograms (TG) were obtained by heating the polymer and copolymer samples in air at 10 °C /min. It was found that the all three homopolymaleimides showed single step degradation, while the copolymaleimides showed a step-by-step degradation. The temperature for initials decomposition T_i , final decomposition T_f and maximum rate of weight loss, T_{max} determined for TGA. The thermal stability data of homo and copolymaleimides are given in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. Thermal behaviour of homopolymaleimides

Polymer	T_i	T_{max}	T_f
HP ₁	210	320	450
HP ₂	230	340	480
HP ₃	240	350	500

Table 4. Thermal behaviour of copolymaleimides

Polymer	T_i	T_{max}	T_f
CP ₁	185	260	300
	300	400	480
CP ₂	190	290	310
	310	400	480
CP ₃	200	300	320
	320	400	500

The TGA results show that the homopolymaleimide of all three (substituted nitrophenyl) maleimides are more thermal stable than the corresponding copolymaleimides. This is attributed the incorporation of the flexible -CH₂-C- linkage in to the chain back bone at the copolymer in contrast to the homopolymer which bear cyclic imide in the polymer chain.

The TGA results showed that the decomposition temperature increases with the increasing the content of NPMI.

Experimental

Materials : Maleic anhydride (SRL, extra pure) was first recrystallized from chloroform and then further purified by sublimation at 54 °C. *o*-, *m*- and *p*-Nitro anilines (SRL, pure) were used as received. MMA (SRL, A.R.) was shaken two to three times with 5% NaOH to eliminate hydroquinone inhibitor, dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ for 6 h and distilled. The head and tail fraction were discarded. AIBN (spectrochem) was recrystallized twice from methanol prior to use. DMF, THF, methanol, etc. used in the present work were of analytical grade and purify better than 90 mol% and were used as received.

Measurements : ¹H NMR spectra of monomer and polymer samples were taken in DMSO-*d*₆ on a Bruker DPX-200/DPX-300 spectrometer at 200/300 MHz. The internal reference used was TMS. FT-IR spectra of the monomer and polymer sample were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC (4000–400 cm⁻¹) FT-IR spectrometer, using a KBr pellet technique. The viscosity measurements were carried out in DMF at 25 ± 0.2 °C, using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. Elemental analysis was made on Carlo Erbe Model NA 500 series analyzer. The thermograms in air obtained on a Mettler TA-3000 system, at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

***N*-(Substituted-nitrophenyl)maleamic acid (NPMA)** : Take a well-stirred solution of 2-, 3- or 4-substituted nitro aniline (13.8 g, 0.1 mol) in DMF, the solution of maleic anhydride (9.8 g, 0.1 mol) in DMF was gradually added over a period of 10 min. Then the mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature. The resulting solution was poured into a large amount of crushed ice to precipitate crude NPMA. The crude NPMA was filtered, dried and then recrystallized from ethanol to obtained pure NPMA.

***N*-(Substituted-nitrophenyl)maleimide (NPMI)** : Cyclo-dehydration of the maleamic acid, an intermediate to maleimide was carried out by treating former with conc. H₂SO₄ and P₂O₅. Then this solution poured in crushed ice obtained to solid NPMI was precipitate. The crude NPMI was filtered and washed with 10% NaHCO₃ solution and dried at 60–70 °C and then recrystallized from ethanol to obtained pure NPMI.

- 1(a) *N*-(2-Nitrophenyl)maleamic acid : yield 70%, m.p. 145 °C
- (b) *N*-(2-Nitrophenyl)maleimide : yield 62%, m.p. 120 °C
- 2(a) *N*-(3-Nitrophenyl)maleamic acid : yield 80%, m.p. 165 °C
- (b) *N*-(3-Nitrophenyl)maleimide : yield 69%, m.p. 192 °C
- 3(a) *N*-(4-Nitrophenyl)maleamic acid : yield 79%, m.p. 145 °C

(b) *N*-(4-Nitrophenyl)maleimide : yield 62%, m.p. 205 °C

Polymerization : Radical homopolymerization of substituted NPMI (0.02 mol, 5.76 g), were carried out with AIBN as free radical initiator in THF (100 ml) in a round bottom flask. Reaction mixture was refluxed at 65 °C for 24 h. The homopolymer of NPMI was isolated by precipitation in methanol containing water. The precipitated homopolymer was washed with methanol several times and dried in a vacuum oven.

Copolymerization : The reaction was carried out in the round bottom flask in equimolar amount of substituted NPMI and MMA in 110 ml THF and was refluxed after adding 25 mg AIBN at 65 °C for 24 h. The copolymer precipitated in methanol containing water mixture. The precipitated copolymer was filter and washed with methanol several times and dried.

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References

1. H. T. Cheng and G. Q. Zhao, *J. Poly. Sci., Part A : Polym. Chem.*, 1992, **30**, 2181; H. M. Li and S. A. Lin, *J. Macromol. Sci., Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2000, **A37**, 1475; T. M. Pyriadi and A. S. Hamad, *Polymer*, 1996, **37**, 5283; L. A. White, J. W. Weber and L. J. Mathias, *Polym. Bull.*, 2001, **46**, 463; O. Tsutomu, S. Kazuki and T. Hiromoni, *J. Poly. Sci., Part A : Polym. Chem.*, 1998, **36**, 2001; C. B. Patel, N. I. Malek and S. L. Oswal, *J. Macromol. Sci., Part A : Pure and Applied Chemistry*, 2006, **43**, 289; D. C. Wan and J. L. Huang, *J. Poly. Sci., Part A : Polym. Chem.*, 1999, **37**, 2755; H. B. Chen, Z. R. Peng, P. S. Liu and H. M. Li, *China Synth. Resin Plastics*, 2003, **17**, 41; L. Chunqing, L. Huaming and L. Pengsheng *J. Macromol. Sci., Part A : Pure and Applied Chemistry*, 2004, **A41**, 1161.
2. J. Xinqiao, P. Yanwan and H. Junlian, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A : Polym. Chem.*, 1998, **36**, 1291; L. Takao, N. Tsutomu, F. Wakichi and T. Masao, *J. Appl. Poly. Sci.*, 1996, **60**, 37.
3. J. Y. Chang, T. J. Kim and M. J. Han, *Polymer*, 1997, **38**, 4651; C. J. Feger, M. M. Khojasteh and J. E. McGrath, "Polyimides : Materials, Chemistry and Characterization", 1989.
4. C. E. Scroog, *J. Polym. Sci. (Macromol. Rev.)*, 1976, **11**, 161; K. L. Mittal (ed.), "Polyimides, Synthesis : Characterization and Application", Plenum Press, New York, 1984, Vol. 1.
5. P. O. Tawney, R. Synder, R. P. Conger, K. A. Leibrand, C. H. Stitler and A. R. Williams, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 15; R. C. P. Cubbon, *Polymer*, 1965, **6**, 419; J. M. Barrales-Rienda, J. I. Gonzalez De La Campa and J. Gonzalez Ramos, *J. Macromol. Sci. Chem.*, 1977, **A11**, 267; K. Kagawa, T. Oishi, K. Matsusaki and M. Fujimoto, *Polymer*, 1995, **36**, 948.
6. A. Matsumoto, T. Kubota and T. Otsu, *Polymer*, 1990, **23**, 4508.